

Exploring Nature as an Assassin in Yeshe Dorje Thongshi's Select Works

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Nature is a source of beauty, mystery and suspense. It works both as a healer and a killer. One finds never-ending peace amidst nature and the same may bring unexpected death and trauma. Lorenz said that Nature is indeed “red in tooth and claw”. The calamitous demeanor of nature is feared, worshiped and even abhorred. Behaving like an assassin, Nature also attempts to teach the human beings to fight against any hazard they face. The intimacy of the ethnic communities with ecology help them to feel and predict about the natural calamities. The artists and writers capture the moments of disastrous occurrences as well as beautify them with colours and words. Yeshe Dorje Thongshi, one of the beloved writers in Assam, belongs to Sherdukpen community of Arunachal Pradesh. Thongshi portrays Nature both as tranquil and terrible in his creative works. He depicts ecological consciousness and the lack of it amongst the people. This paper is an attempt to explore the nature as an assassin in some of Yeshe Dorje Thongshi's works. It will study the wrath of nature in Thongshi's novel *Mishing* (2008) and two of his short stories, respectively *Bah Phular Gondh* and *Pema Sikari*. The paper will analyse different looks of nature as an assassin in the select works. It will also study the revengefulness of Nature. The portrayal of the increasing lack of ecological consciousness among the people in Thongshi's works will also be explored.

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